

SYNERGIC INTEGRATION AND EXTRA-ROLE BEHAVIOR OF EMPLOYEES IN
BPO'S – A MICRO STUDY IN SHIVAMOGGA

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Abstract

There has empirical research evidence to believe that employees' behavior which is beyond traditional territory of job description does contribute to the organizational effectiveness. That is why the extra role behavior is a competitive advantage and has been gaining rapid significance as an effective tool for improving organizational efficiency. In this highly competitive era, employees proactive role is of paramount necessity and the harmony among the group is an added benefit for achieving the long term success for the organization. This paper evaluates the behavior and performance of the employees which helps in achieving long term success for the business. This study is an attempt to analyze the synergic integration of the employees and proves to be a significant tool for the overall growth of the business. The paper uses multiple variables and various questionnaires to evaluate and analyze the synergic integration and extra role behavior of employees in Bpo's.

Keywords: *Synergic Integration, Extra Role Behavior, Job Involvement and Organizational Citizenship*

Introduction

There has been a lot of change in the conduction of the business in recent years. Firms are engaged in undertaking various activities which enhance the company's growth in general and

Employee's growth in particular. Achieving core competency and competitive advantage is now a day's necessitate for the business. Working unique as a team and maintaining harmony among the group is the call of the hour. Employees are motivated not only to do their limited obligation but they are stimulated to achieve the target work and provide the result beyond the expectation. Frequent training programmes are conducted by the organization to imbibe the necessary skills among the employees. Firms are providing training to the employees to make them more and more familiar to the organization goals and values. New employees are greeted with full heart and comfortable environment is provided to them to easily get accustomed to the culture of the organization. Apart from their regular curriculum, employees are required to participate in various other programmes like managing quiz, conduction of fest e.t.c. Stress management is given due importance and proper training is given for the same to increase the organizational effectiveness as a whole. Frequent tour programmes are conducted by the firms to give employees a sense of togetherness and make each other's company comfortable, which plays a vital role in maintaining the harmony among the organization. Continuous performance appraisal programmes are undertaken by the firm to award the various employees, who worked in an appreciative manner for the development of the organization as a whole. Frequent reward programmes ensures the acknowledgement of the services of the employees and due motivation is provided in the name of promotion and perks. There is continuous check of HRM Department to ensure that the employees are well accustomed to the culture of the organization and due preference is given to the safety of the employees.

Objective

1. To analyze the synergic integration among the employees as an tool to meet organizational commitments and values
2. To evaluate the extra role behavior of employees in improving the organizational effectiveness and success.

Statement of the Problem:

There has been a significant change in the role of the employees over the years. Firms appreciate employee's proactive behavior as compare to reactive behavior within the firm. Firms are engaged to inculcate the organizational goals and values among the employees. They are provided with various training programmes in induction process about the core value of the

organization. Quality in work and management of time is of paramount importance. Stress management is the another side of the coin and due importance is given for reduction of the same.

Scope of the Study

The study is conducted only for shimoga city and various questionnaires were formed and were duly analyzed before framing any conclusion. Mainly primary data were used to analyze the same. A sample of 50 has been taken on a random basis.

Hypothesis

H₀ -There is no direct relationship between synergic integration of employees and organizational commitments and value.

H₁ -There is a direct relationship between synergic integration of employees and organizational commitments and value

H₀ -There is no direct relationship between the proportion of extra role played by the employee and the success achieved by the organization

H₁ - There is a direct relationship between the proportion of extra role played by the employee and the success achieved by the organization

Table 1. Employee Profile

Designation	Male (%)	Female (%)	Average Age	Educational Background(%)				Total	Percentage
				PUC	Degree	PG	Others		
Managing Director	39(78)	11(22)	40	-	16(32)	32(64)	2(4)	50	100
Manager	33(66)	17(34)	36	-	34(68)	15(30)	1(2)	50	100

Assistant Manager	23(46)	27(54)	32	-	40(80)	10(20)	-	50	100
Group/Team Leader	24(48)	26(52)	28	1	46(92)	3(6)	-	50	100
Team Coordinator	22(44)	28(56)	26	2	41(82)	3(6)	4(8)	50	100
Team Employees	25(50)	25(50)	24	17	18(36)	10(20)	5(10)	50	100
System Operators	33(66)	17(34)	25	27	10(20)	1(2)	12(2 4)	50	100
Support Staff	15(30)	35(70)	29	25	2(4)	-	23(4 6)	50	100
Total(%)	26.75 (53.5 0)	23.25 (46.5 0)		9(18)	25.875(51. 75)	9.25(1 8.50)	5.87 5(34. 51)	50	100

The above table reveals that majority of Managing Director are male as compare to their female counterparts. This is due to the fact that women counterparts withdraw in the early stages as they had got more commitments towards family as compare to the male counterparts. As far as their education background is considered majority of them are P.G holders as they complete their post degree education in correspondence courses, as it attracts high profile job in corporate sector. As far as others are considered, these are the persons who have got high knowledge about

their respective areas and due to their high experience over the years regarding the subject ensures them higher post. Manager is the one who manages the whole organization in a well framed and well structured manner. Here we can see that the picture does not change too much either, but it clearly reveals that degree education is more as compare to post graduate and there has been decline in the average age. In the designation of assistant manager we can see that there is sudden increase in the female members as compare to their male counterparts, it is due to the fact that till the age of 32 the family commitments are limited and they have an self-esteem to grow in the sector. That urge of getting success is more as compare to the later part of their career. In team leader or group leader we can find that share of women employees are more as they don't marry till the age of 28 and there is hunger to get success and it prompts them to take them challenges in a better planned way and it motivates them to turn it the same as an opportunity. The majority of team leader are studying degree only as the don't have that much inspiration to study more as enjoy the present work in a pleasant manner and the need of further education does not comes into the picture. In team coordinator , we can find the majority of persons are females and they are candidates with 2 or 3 years experience in the above said process and thus there inclined towards success is more as majority of them enter in degree level. Team level employees are the fresh graduates who have just completed their graduates and have join the organization. Hence we can see equal proportion of male and female members in the process. In system operators the majority of them are male and the level of education is degree but still we can see many diploma holders, ITI holders possessing the job. When it comes to support staff we can see high number of female candidates due to the nature of work and we can also find that the majority of them are possessing PUC or SSLC, due to which we can see that there has been increase in the share of others.

H₀ -There is no direct relationship between synergic integration of employees and organizational commitments and value

H₁ - There is a direct relationship between synergic integration of employees and organizational commitments and value

Table 2

Synergic Integrations	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Percentage
Quality in allocated work	20	40	20	7	3	100
Finishing the Job in adequate time	16	33	29	12	10	100
Group Cohesiveness	40	30	17	11	2	100
Adhering to the needs of subordinates	34	29	18	13	6	100
Balancing of Stress	22	19	30	19	10	100
Acting Proactively	42	30	14	8	6	100
Sense of Belonging towards Organization	37	26	20	13	4	100
Frequent Performance Appraisal of Employees	41	33	16	7	3	100

Adhering to the needs of clients	37	34	25	4	-	100
Inspiring & Appreciating Constructive ideas of subordinates	12	23	37	17	11	100
Acceptance of organizational values	33	24	23	12	8	100
Total	30.36	29.18	22.93	11.81	5.72	100

Result Discussion

The above table reveals that quality maintained in the allocated work ensures a synergic integration in employees. The quality of work ensures long term customer availability and continuous success to the business organization. Apart from finishing the job with quality the next best thing is to finish the job within in the allocated time as well. Before the time, finishing of work is much appreciated as compare to the work finished at the time or after the time. It ensures that works are completed in timely framed manner with proper quality. Hence we can see 29 percent of the total respondents agreeing for the same. The firms who are working in group achieve more results as compare to other firms. Togetherness creates more harmony and more positive results for any business organization. The same has been shown in the above table as more percentage has been allocated to the strongly agreed variable. Developing alone does not matter, but developing in group is what it matters. Adhering to the needs of subordinates ensures long term growth for any business firms. Hence we can find more percentage for the same. Managing the stress is now days of paramount importance and various soft skill programmes have been imbibed in various corporate sectors to ensure the overall growth of the employees and business. In firms, employees who act above the expectation of people carries huge credentials as it make the customer surprise in a positive manner. Hence we can see it carries

more share. Every organization works efficiently and effectively only and only if we assume that company belongs to us. This creates a sense of responsibility, interest and above all hunger to achieve more. Frequent appraisal of employees' performance results in continuous improvements and helps to achieve more positive results. Hence more share has been allocated for the same. Client is the root market for the firms. Satisfying them is of paramount importance and satisfying them takes a huge task. According to the needs of clients the situation changes and firm should be flexible enough to get it adjusted to the needs of the business. Change is a continuous process and continuous research is of paramount importance. This can only be developed through the continuous motivation for the research and same can be achieved through providing proper direction. Hence we can see high share of acceptance, but in firms the major problem is the internal politics existing among the employees as this is high among the employee. Hence the constructive ideas will be limited. Acceptance of organization value and working for the same ensures the uniqueness in the goal of employees and employers and helps in building of the organization as a whole. Hence we can see the share of strongly agreed is more as compared to others. **Hence we can conclude that there is a direct relationship between synergic integration of employees and organizational commitments and value. Therefore we can find that alternative hypothesis is accepted.**

H₀- There is no direct relationship between the proportion of extra role played by the employee and the success achieved by the organization

H₁- There is a direct relationship between the proportion of extra role played by the employee and the success achieved by the organization

Table no 3

Extra Role Behaviors	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Percentage
Proper utilization of	28	46	20	4	2	100

human resources						
Cooperative towards new employees	27	22	19	15	7	100
Participation in Decision making	13	24	43	7	3	100
Working above expectation	17	19	37	14	13	100
Keeping personal and professional Difference	33	27	20	13	7	100
Participating in Extra Circular Activity	37	22	12	18	11	100
Understanding and helping other Team/Groups	23	26	17	19	15	100
Total(%)	25.42	26.57	24.00	12.85	8.28	100

Results and Discussion

The extra role played by the employees apart from their usual work ensures long term success for the business. The above table clearly reveals that as an outcome of their extra role, they can ensure more success to the organization by optimally utilizing the resources of the organization. The resources may be manpower, time, and financial resources etc. Hence we can

see high number of strong agree and agreed variable. The coordinational behavior towards the new employees is the extra role played by the employees. They have to make them feel in home and try to make them as comfortable as possible by behaving well with them in the professional circuit. The firm will be also be beneficial if the employees participate in decision making process as the employees are roots of the business and they will be able to know pros and cons of every decision. Hence their participation in the decision making is an added benefit. Hence we can see huge amount of agree share. But some time their decision ability is doubted as majority of them don't have experience in the same. Hence we can see high amount of neutral variable. Working above expectation is a proactive step and it attracts not only fellow employees but also the customer. Hence the employee should be proactive. This creates more energy among the group and is an added benefit, but some time the employer's feels that it is not an extra behavior role and sees them as the part and parcel of their work. Hence we can see some variation in disagree and strongly disagree aspect. Keeping the personal and professional bias is an added role imbibed on the employee as it ensures harmony among the group and it ensures long term growth of the firm. Hence we can see high amount of strongly agreed share. Apart from the daily operations the firm conducts many other activities to improve and market their company in the business world. These are frequent quiz, fest etc. The participants are the employees of the business who are working in the firm. These are an added responsibility for the employees. In firm helping our groups is normal thing but helping other teams and other team members is an extra role played by the firm. Employees should be motivated further to work with various groups and team members.

Hence we can conclude that there is a direct relationship between the proportion of extra role played by the employee and the success achieved by the organization. Therefore we can find that alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion

The competition going on within the firms to succeed has changed the way of doing the business. Managing the stress and extra role played by the employee goes in long term for ensuring the success of the business. Apart from their active role, it is the proactive role played by the employee which is a major tool in deciding the faith of the business. The synergic

integration among the employee is the call of the hour. The harmony among the firm and its employees ensures the positive growth of the business firm. Various training and development programmes are conducted within the firm to ensure that the employees are adhering to the common goal and values of the business firm. It has been seen in recent times that there have been frequent increase in the turnover of the employees and the reason being the high level of stress which is almost unmanageable for the new employee. Hence it's very important that frequent stress management training should be conducted by the firms to ensure there is low turnover among the employees as it reduces the cost of training to the new employees. It has been observed that companies are indulged in various other extra curriculum activities it ensures that the company marketing is done in an appreciated manner. It may be in the form of frequent conduction of management fest, Business Quiz etc. For all this type of activity the participation of employees is a essence. While doing performance appraisal the contribution of employees are duly analyzed and ratings are provided on the basis of the same

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